

D1.1. A roadmap to transfer knowledge gained on pure culture of purple phototrophic bacteria to the application in non-axenic mixed cultures, including strategies to fill knowledge gaps.

1. Context and goals

The PurpleGain COST Action aims to connect the stakeholders of the entire value chain from waste streams to end-products propelled by Phototrophic Purple Bacteria (PPB). In this network of excellence, we will make use of the state-of-the-art knowledge and know-how generated at the most prominent European research institutes in the field of PPB-based resource recovery. Scientific, technological, and analytical approaches will be harmonized on this interactive platform to bridge experts of pure-culture and mixed-culture biotechnologies in Europe and overseas. PurpleGain will establish PPB science and technologies at the root of circularity and bio-based economy initiatives driven by the European Union (EU) from thorough scientific to high technology readiness levels (TRL). Through PPB, we will demonstrate the effective operability of bio-based resource recovery across the continuum of pure-culture, co-culture and mixed-culture biotechnologies.

The goal of this roadmap is to elaborate an integrated strategy allowing the transfer of extensive knowledge already available at pure culture level, and addressing fundamental aspects of PPB metabolism, in an industrial context where PPB are used for the development of applied biotechnologies.

Fundamental metabolic knowledge is currently abundant but not sufficiently used to develop, design, optimise and implement mixed or pure culture PPB-based bioprocesses. The main obstacles to a more extensive utilisation of the fundamental knowledge in application were identified during preparation of the PurpleGain COST action and highlighted during the first bi-annual meeting of the action Working Group 1. Three main obstacles were noted as critical, and strategies to overcome them are discussed in this roadmap:

1. The lack of a common language between researchers/stakeholders active in the purple bacteria field
2. The lack of knowledge regarding the interactions of purple bacteria with other organisms or among themselves in mixed cultures
3. The lack of molecular tools enabling the study of mixed cultures that have purple bacteria

2. The first obstacle - Definitions and common language

Determining the efficiency of a process involves various crucial parameters such as the quantity of photons used to illuminate photobioreactors, the amount of nutrients supplied and consumed, and even culture yield and productivity. However, multiple definitions and units are used for these parameters between the various PPB fields of study (biophysics, biochemistry, biotechnology engineering, etc.). These terms and the lack of consensus within the PPB community creates important exchange difficulties between researchers. For instance, in the context of wastewater treatment plants, a biotechnological engineer may find it appropriate to express bioproduct production as the amount of bioproduct per grams of COD (Chemical Oxygen Demand) resulting in units of grams/COD rather than grams/liter. Similarly, most of the parameters influencing PPB culturing or used for efficiency evaluation are affected by this absence of harmonized units. A similar discussion about needs and requirements for better data exchange between fields was also recently addressed regarding wastewater treatment processes.¹

When considering the production of hydrogen (H₂) by photofermentation, different units can be found in the literature, ranging from L H₂ L⁻¹ culture² to g H₂ g⁻¹ substrate³, mol H₂ mol⁻¹ substrate⁴ or even mol H₂ mol⁻¹ nEqC⁵. This variation in units further complicates the comparison of production and yield values, making it more challenging to draw meaningful conclusions. To promote consistency in the literature and facilitate unit interconversion in the future (*e.g.*, through mathematical models), it is crucial to define “the minimum required information”, *i.e.*, the essential information that should be provided when describing the carbon, electron, and light inputs, as well as the productivity of PPB-based bioprocesses.

The amount and quality of light supplied is a crucial parameter in PPB culturing and in photobiotechnologies in general. However, various units can also be encountered in literature such as: W m⁻², lux and μmol of photons m⁻²s⁻¹. The interconversion of these units heavily relies on the spectral characteristics of the light source employed. As a result, to ensure the reproducibility of bioprocesses, it is essential to provide the integrated light spectrum, or a clear and quantitative description of the light source used. To facilitate direct power consumption calculations, watt unit is recommended. When it comes to carbon and electron inputs, it is also necessary to provide detailed information about medium composition. This includes specifying the nature and concentration of the carbon (*e.g.*, in grams of COD per liter) and nitrogen sources used, along with any addition of bicarbonates (g L⁻¹) or CO₂, as they play a significant role in the redox poise.

In addition to these parameters, some information specific to PPB-growth-associated (*e.g.*, microbial protein, photopigments, Q-10 coenzyme) and PPB-growth-independent bioproducts (*e.g.*, H₂, polyhydroxyalkanoates, alginates, 4-aminolevulinic acid) should be included. For example, when reporting hydrogen production, we recommend including the following information: the amount of H₂ produced per liter of culture, the amount of H₂ produced per liter of culture per hour/per day for productivity comparisons, the amount of H₂ produced per gram of substrate consumed, and the amount of H₂ produced per gram of dry weight (DW) or ideally of volatile suspended solid (VSS). A study conducted in 2018 by Vasiliadou *et al.* notably incorporates the above-mentioned parameters and could be used as a reference. As hydrogen is far from being the only valuable compound derived

from PPB, an overview of the minimum information required for various PPB-derived bioproducts is presented in Table 1. By providing these pieces of information, biotechnological engineers would be able, for example, to determine the actual yield of H₂ production in relation to biomass production or substrate consumption. In addition, hydrogen production could also be expressed from a more fundamental perspective in terms of excess electrons dissipated in relation to the reduction state of the biomass. All these parameters would thus make it possible to facilitate the transition towards unit standardization, and therefore enhance the communication and collaboration among researchers in the PPB field. Standardization will also hasten innovation to meet the demands of impending crises that face humanity and require better bioproduction strategies using PPB.

PPB-derived bioproducts	Minimal required information
Hydrogen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The amount of H₂ produced per liter of culture (L H₂ L⁻¹ culture) - The amount of H₂ produced per liter of culture per hour for productivity comparisons (L H₂ L⁻¹ culture h⁻¹) - The amount of H₂ produced per gram of substrate consumed (g H₂ g⁻¹ substrate consumed) - The amount of H₂ produced per gram of DW (L H₂ g⁻¹ DW) - The substrate nature and concentration (<i>e.g.</i>, gCOD L⁻¹ but ideally with a description of major component) - The nature and concentration of the nitrogen source used (gN L⁻¹) - The amount and quality of light supplied (emission spectrum in W m⁻² μm⁻¹, total irradiance in W m⁻²)
Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The amount of PHAs produced per liter of culture (g PHA L⁻¹ culture) - The amount of PHAs produced per gram of substrate consumed (g PHA g⁻¹ substrate consumed) - The amount of PHAs produced per gram of DW (g PHA g⁻¹ DW) - The monomer composition of the polymer (g monomer (HX) g⁻¹ PHA), including at least 3-hydroxybutyrate (HB) and 3-hydroxyvalerate (HV). - The extraction procedure for PHA quantification - The substrate nature and concentration (<i>e.g.</i>, gCOD L⁻¹ but ideally with a description of major component) - The amount and quality of light supplied (emission spectrum in W m⁻² μm⁻¹, total irradiance in W m⁻²)
Photopigments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The amount of pigments produced per gram of DW (g pigments g⁻¹ DW) and the pigment composition of the biomass (<i>e.g.</i>, g BChl g⁻¹ DW). - The total concentration of carotenoids (g carotenoids g⁻¹ DW). - The substrate nature and concentration (<i>e.g.</i>, gCOD L⁻¹ but ideally with a description of major component). - The absorbance spectrum of the pigments extracted with acetone or ethanol (in Abs units, minimum range 400-1100 nm) - The amount and quality of light supplied (emission spectrum in W m⁻² μm⁻¹, total irradiance in W m⁻²)
Microbial protein	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The amount of proteins produced per liter of culture (g protein L⁻¹ culture)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The amount of proteins produced per liter of culture per hour for productivity comparisons (g protein L⁻¹ culture h⁻¹) - The amount of proteins produced per gram of substrate consumed (g protein g⁻¹ substrate consumed) - The amount of proteins produced per gram of DW (g protein g⁻¹ DW) - The biomass composition in essential amino acids (EAs) (<i>e.g.</i>, g valine g⁻¹ DW) - The substrate nature and concentration (<i>e.g.</i>, gCOD L⁻¹ but ideally with a description of major component) - The nature and concentration of the nitrogen source used (gN L⁻¹) - The amount and quality of light supplied (emission spectrum in W m⁻² μm⁻¹, total irradiance in W m⁻²)
Alginates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The amount of alginates produced per liter of culture (g ALG L⁻¹ culture) - The amount of alginates produced per liter of culture per hour for productivity comparisons (g ALG L⁻¹ culture h⁻¹) - The amount of alginates produced per gram of substrate consumed (g ALG g⁻¹ substrate consumed) - The amount of proteins produced per gram of DW (g ALG g⁻¹ DW) - The amount of exopolysaccharides per gram of DW (g EPS g⁻¹ DW) - The extraction procedure for alginates quantification - The substrate nature and concentration (<i>e.g.</i>, gCOD L⁻¹ but ideally with a description of major component) - The amount and quality of light supplied (emission spectrum in W m⁻² μm⁻¹, total irradiance in W m⁻²)
4-Aminolevulinic acid	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The amount of 4-aminolevulinic acid produced per liter of culture (g 4-ALA L⁻¹ culture) - The amount of 4-aminolevulinic acid produced per liter of culture per hour for productivity comparisons (g 4-ALA L⁻¹ culture h⁻¹) - The substrate nature and concentration (<i>e.g.</i>, gCOD L⁻¹ but ideally with a description of major component) - The amount and quality of light supplied (emission spectrum in W m⁻² μm⁻¹, total irradiance in W m⁻²)
Q-10 coenzyme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The amount of Q-10 coenzyme produced per liter of culture (g Q-10 L⁻¹ culture) - The amount of Q-10 coenzyme produced per liter of culture per hour for productivity comparisons (g Q-10 L⁻¹ culture h⁻¹) - The extraction procedure for Q-10 coenzyme quantification - The substrate nature and concentration (<i>e.g.</i>, gCOD L⁻¹ but ideally with a description of major component) - The amount and quality of light supplied (emission spectrum in W m⁻² μm⁻¹, total irradiance in W m⁻²)

Table 1. Minimal required information for PPB-derived bioproducts.

In order to find a common language and unify different definitions of efficiency, (from quantum efficiency of photon capture, energy and electron transfer⁶ to bioproduct per gram of COD, it is desirable to construct simple mathematical rate-network models that relate these efficiencies. Such models would be didactic for all disciplines involved in the consortium and would illustrate the information content of each definition of efficiency. Further, the models can lead to a better understanding of optimization principles.

Additional point that might be discussed in a future updated version:

- Expression of quantitative targets for the production of PPB-growth-associated (e.g., PPB biomass, PHA, photopigments) and PPB growth-independent bioproducts (e.g., H₂)

3. The second obstacle - Effects of synergy and inhibition between microbes in synthetic, open or natural communities

Another important point to be addressed is the definition of a consortium or a community of organisms. While fundamental aspects of the metabolism are usually addressed in pure cultures, environmental-based engineered processes generally do not operate in axenic conditions. Axenic conditions refer to cultivation conditions that maintain a pure culture of microorganisms. In other words, the culture only contains a single species of organism, and no contaminating organisms are present in the culture. One might argue that a more relevant situation is the “synthetic microbial community”, defined as a mixture of different species/strains of bacteria creating a defined community of microorganisms. Synthetic ecology is a growing area that bridges principles of industrial and environmental biotechnologies. It is an important part of bottom-up and top-down approaches for microbiome engineering⁷. The creation of a “synthetic community” starts from pure cultures of the different species of bacteria and only the selected bacteria are effectively members of the community. If no contamination of the synthetic community by other species of bacteria are allowed, this community could be considered as axenic. The composition of this synthetic community could evolve in response to the process, especially regarding the proportion of the different members of the community and based on their individual fitness under the applied culture conditions. Such a synthetic and axenic community contrasts with a synthetic but “open” community, created as previously explained, in which the axenicity of the culture is not maintained. In this case, invasions/contaminations by external microorganisms are tolerated, and this open community would of course evolve based on contamination and culture conditions. Finally, the highest species diversity would be obtained working with a “natural community” obtained by sampling natural or engineered environments such as natural ponds or wastewater treatment plants for example. In this case, the community contains a very large number of different species/strains of microorganisms, and the proportion of each is the result of the existing conditions in the sampled environment. Such natural communities can be extensively characterised through various molecular techniques (16S RNA sequencing or shotgun metagenomic analyses as well as metaproteomics) but an exhaustive knowledge of the species present will require advances in various multi-omic techniques.

PPB in aquatic ecosystems are metabolically versatile, and can live in changing trophic, light and oxygen conditions. Microbial consortia dominated by PPB will be a better choice in resource recovery from waste and wastewater than pure cultures of one PPB species (model species). There are several benefits of this approach: (1) cheaper management of the PPB and lack of the need of sterile medium for their growth, (2) better use of organic matter and other intermediate products of the degradation due to the trophic interactions, like symbiosis (synergy), commensalism, even competition between the participants of the mixed culture. By using different microscopic and molecular methods, some of the microbial communities in the mixed culture can be determined as bioindicators of the quality and quantity of the expected products during the processes in the bioreactors. An example is the use of fluorescence In situ Hybridization (FISH) analysis in biogas production⁸. Consortia of algae and bacteria are used in wastewater decontamination and transformation into different products⁹.

Recent successful “proof of concept” studies for the implementation of consortia and even (open) mixed cultures to produce industrially relevant biocompounds demonstrate the success of bench to pilot and then industrial scale production. In the field of mixed-culture fermentation, it is now possible to produce lactic acid at a high titre without sterilisation¹⁰. The knowledge gained can be transferred for the development of PPB-based co-culture and mixed-culture biotechnologies, while the aforementioned specific challenges intrinsic to carbon, electron and light inputs are addressed.

An interesting approach to overcome the biological competition problems is to use stringent cultivating conditions to benefit the microorganisms of the consortium that are key for the biotechnological process under evaluation. As PPB are vastly metabolically versatile, it is possible to set various stringent conditions at a time. For example, a mixed-culture was used for the biodegradation of emerging pollutants present in a synthetic medium lacking a dissolved nitrogen source. The anaerobic photobioreactor was illuminated with infrared lamps and the reactor walls were covered with specific UV-Vis filters. This way, only photoheterotrophic and nitrogen-fixating microorganisms were able to grow. Under these conditions, the mixed culture was highly enriched in PPB, accounting for up to 94% of the total 16S rRNA gene copies of bacteria in the consortium, with *Rhodospseudomonas palustris* as the dominant species of the system (68%), and *Blastochloris sulfoviridis* and *Rhodoplanes elegans* as secondary PPB species¹¹.

Another important consideration when cultivating bacteria in engineered conditions is the phenomenon of genetic drift or genomic adaptation. Bacteria very efficiently adapt to environmental conditions through mutation or genome rearrangement. During long-term cultivation in acetate containing medium, it has been demonstrated that *Rhodospirillum rubrum* amplifies some region of its genome containing genes required for the photoassimilation of acetate¹². This genome rearrangement made the adapted strain less sensitive to light stress and less dependent on bicarbonate assimilation for its redox homeostasis under high light. This demonstrates that the genome plasticity of PNSB is high, and they can quickly adapt to specific environment. In biotechnological application, this adaptation could represent an opportunity, if one wants to improve growth rate in certain conditions by adapting its strains, but it could also represent a threat. Indeed, if the biotechnological application relies on the cultivation of bacteria under some specific stress, for higher pigment or PHA production for example, adaptation might decrease sensitivity to the stress and consequently also the yield of the bioprocess itself. Genomic adaptation capacity of PNSB should thus be more extensively studied to allow evaluation of this phenomenon on bioprocesses, especially if they are to be performed under continuous mode. Batch operation with inoculation from naive

strains but also application of variable culture condition could also be used to prevent yield decrease due to strain adaptation to stress.

The speed at which *Rhodospirillum rubrum* adapted to acetate condition (+/- 50 generations) in addition to many other observations (such as light stress adaptation or sequential assimilation of carbon sources supplied as mixtures in multiple strains) also raise the question of the existence of sub-populations in PNSB cultures. Metabolic heterogeneity, defined as the coexistence of multiple metabolically differentiated sub-populations in a culture, is increasingly considered as a general rule rather than an exception in bacteria cultures^{13,14}. It has however been very poorly studied in PNSB although such heterogeneity in metabolism is associated with decrease in the general yield of the process. Methods based on protein biosensors, flow cytometry or molecular imaging could be used to study metabolic heterogeneity in pure culture but also in community in which this phenomenon should also be more extensively studied. Monitoring of genomic stability/adaptation as well as development of metabolic subpopulations is a crucial to understand the long-term stability of PNSB in bioprocesses.

Proposition of additional subject which might also be discussed in a future version of roadmap:

- Examples of synergy/inhibition among different species, based on growth, product formation or desired attributes.
- Compilation of existing knowledge and models for mechanisms of cooperation/competition between species and identifying gaps in our current knowledge.
- Substrate and other conditions that may be preferred to modulate the species composition of consortia or to maintain pure cultures.
- How to maintain desired functionality in open/natural community and favour PPBs?
- Cost associated with axenicity? Decrease in productivity associated with contamination? (Food) safety associated to contamination?
- Strains conservation

4. The third obstacle - Molecular tools for consortium follow up/improvement.

To foster and optimise the production of high added-value compounds, process engineers need to understand the behaviour of their bioreactors. In most cases, information required in this context is already available showing that more efficient data sharing should be implemented. Analytical capacity of bioprocesses is available but more targeted strategies should be to define sets of required and sufficient parameters. These need to then be recorded to give more extensive real time monitoring and control to processes. Process analytical technology (PAT) is a core competence in industrial biotechnology, enabling a deeper knowledge on and control of bioprocesses in parallel to securing good manufacturing practices (GMP). Transferring PAT strategies to PPB-based pure/co/mixed-culture biotechnologies will consist of an important target.

Bioprocesses relying on bacterial consortia are obviously more difficult to analyse than pure cultures. To obtain a complete understanding of interactions between members of a consortium or identify if

labour division or substrate preferences appear when bacteria are transferred from pure culture to consortium meta-omic analyses are necessary. Metagenomics is a well-developed approach and helps in following the composition of a consortium in response to modification of processing conditions. Metatranscriptomic and metaproteomic can also be used to obtain a better view of the metabolic activity of the different members of the consortium, allowing us to obtain species specific data. Such data needs to be properly handle also considering the consortium composition evolution. Transposon mutant libraries are also very useful in defining metabolic activities that take place in a bacterium under different conditions (Tn-Seq). Methods were recently developed, called bar-coded TnSeq, which introduce bar codes in the transposon mutation process, facilitating the sequencing step and thus allowing larger analyses to be performed. Taking into account the enormous diversity of bar codes available in such transposon mutant libraries, bar-coded Tn-Seq analyses can also be performed on synthetic consortium. Such analyses would allow high throughput monitoring of metabolic changes that may arise from pure culture mixing and bridge the gap between pure culture metabolic knowledge and metabolism of PPB communities.

Experimental work will also be required to better characterise processes and select the minimal sets of parameters needed for proper monitoring. An essential list of microbial/metabolic information should be identified to design, monitor and control PPB biotechnologies. From these, targeted analyses should be engaged to determine at microbial and metabolic levels the activity/abundance of key pathway players. These analytics should be species specific and/or performed at single cell level. Omics/spectroscopy tools should be used and linked with consortium compositional studies. Such data will lead to the description of minimal set of metabolic reporters which could be used to feed metabolic model allowing bioprocess outcome prediction and real time predictive control.

5. Conclusion

This roadmap, prepared in the context of the PurpleGain COST action, reflect subject researcher might focus on discuss further in order to improve the capacity of data sharing between fundamental metabolism researcher and engineers or even industrial plant. In this document, we already touched many aspects of what should be done to use fundamentals knowledge more efficiently in bioprocesses development. This document is of course only a first version as many additional points to be discussed were continuously raised along the preparation of this document. It will thus probably be necessary to update this document in the future, but also to work on case studies in which our principle should be applied and which should demonstrate the rationality of the strategic view we developed here. This would make PNSB an example for the many bioprocesses field which suffer from the same limitations.

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